

Leadership Qualities and Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers

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Abstract. This study investigated the relationship between leadership qualities and classroom behavioral management strategies among public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Davao City. Utilizing a non-experimental quantitative research design with a descriptive correlation approach, the research involved 120 teachers aged 30–50 years, with 10–20 years of teaching experience, selected through purposive sampling. Data were collected via validated and reliable survey questionnaires and analyzed using mean, Pearson R correlation, and Multiple Linear Regression. Findings revealed that teachers exhibited high levels of leadership qualities, including empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness, which were strongly correlated with effective classroom behavioral management strategies. Regression analysis further confirmed that these leadership indicators significantly influenced classroom management outcomes. The study concluded that tough leadership qualities are essential for successful classroom management, highlighting the importance of fostering such skills among educators to address behavioral challenges and enhance student engagement in public elementary schools in Maa District, Davao City.

KEY WORDS

1. Leadership Qualities 2. Classroom Behavioral Management 3. Public Elementary School Teachers

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1. Introduction

Teachers' leadership qualities are crucial for effective classroom behavior management, as they establish a foundation of respect, trust, and authority essential for maintaining order and fostering a positive learning environment. Strong leadership skills enable teachers to set clear expectations, implement consistent rules, and respond to disruptive behavior with confidence and fairness. However, several public elementary school teachers faced various challenges in managing classroom behaviors. Some teachers struggle to connect with learners leading to increased behavioral issues, and some also find it hard to communicate with their learners which leads to misunderstandings and a lack of clarity in classroom expectations. Another, some public elementary teachers specially the new ones find it challenging to address diverse learner needs, leading to disengagement and misbehavior as well as they struggle to enforce rules and maintain classroom discipline. Relatively, the leadership qualities of public elementary teachers affect their classroom behavioral management. For example, teacher's empathy enables

them to connect with learners on an emotional level, fostering a supportive and inclusive environment that can preemptively address behavioral issues by understanding and addressing learners' underlying emotional needs (Collie et al., 2019). Another, their effective communication is essential for setting clear expectations and providing consistent feedback, which helps create a structured learning environment, reducing misunderstandings and misbehavior (Sezer et al., 2019). Also, teacher's adaptability allows them to modify their teaching strategies to meet diverse learner needs, maintaining engagement and minimizing disruptions by ensuring all learners can access the curriculum in a way that suits their learning styles (Richards, 2020). Lastly, teacher's assertiveness, is considered crucial for enforcing rules and maintaining discipline without creating a hostile atmosphere, ensuring that boundaries are respected and the classroom remains orderly and conducive to learning (Wilson Holligan, 2019). Teachers who lack leadership qualities often struggle with effective classroom behavior management, leading to a range of issues that can impact learner learning and engagement. In global context, educational discrepancies significantly affect teachers' ability to exhibit leadership qualities crucial for effective classroom management. For example, in Thailand, the leadership qualities of public elementary teachers, particularly in terms of empathy and effective communication, face significant challenges due to cultural and systemic factors. Thai teachers often encounter large class sizes, which make it difficult to establish individual connections with learners, thereby limiting the capacity for empathetic engagement. This is compounded by the hierarchical nature of Thai society, where teachers are traditionally seen as authoritative figures, potentially hindering open and empathetic interactions (Nguyen et al., 2020). Effective communication is further strained by a curriculum heavily focused on rote learning, leaving little room for interactive and learner-centered teaching approaches (Yuenyong Narjaikaew, 2020). Another, public elementary teachers face the dual challenge of maintaining adaptability and assertiveness in a multicultural and multilingual educational context in Malaysia. The Malaysian education system is characterized by its diverse learner population, necessitating a high degree of adaptability among teachers to cater to different cultural backgrounds and learning needs. However, this adaptability is often hindered by rigid curricular demands and standardized assessments, which limit teachers' flexibility in instructional methods (Othman et al., 2019). Assertiveness in classroom management is also a critical issue, as teachers must navigate cultural sensitivities while maintaining discipline. Studies have shown that teachers who balance assertiveness with cultural understanding are more successful in managing classroom behavior and fostering a positive learning environment (Ramli Zain, 2021). In Vietnam, the emphasis on assertiveness and adaptability among public elementary teachers is important for effective classroom behavioral management. Vietnamese teachers are traditionally viewed as authoritative figures, which supports assertiveness in maintaining classroom discipline (Nguyen Tran, 2019). However, this traditional view can sometimes conflict with modern educational practices that encourage more learner-centered learning environments. Adaptability becomes essential as teachers are increasingly required to implement innovative teaching methods and integrate technology into the classroom. The Vietnamese education system is undergoing reforms to support these shifts, including professional development programs that train teachers to be both adaptable and assertive in managing classroom behaviors effectively (Tran et al., 2021). In the context of the Philippine educational system, public elementary teachers often grapple with the challenge of maintaining empathy in a classroom setting marked by diverse socio-

economic backgrounds and large class sizes (Macayan, 2020). It is believed that teachers who exhibit empathy can build stronger relationships with their learners, fostering a supportive and inclusive classroom environment. However, the high learner-to-teacher ratio makes it difficult for teachers to provide individualized attention, leading to potential gaps in addressing the specific emotional needs of learners (Gozum Rustia, 2021). Additionally, issue on effective communication as part of teacher's leadership quality is also present in Philippine educational system. Teachers faced challenges in navigating linguistic diversity and varying levels of language proficiency, particularly in rural and multi-ethnic areas where learners may speak different dialects or languages at home (Pascua Gentry, 2020). This linguistic challenge can hinder clear communication, leading to misunderstandings and misbehavior. Teachers who can effectively communicate and bridge language gaps are better able to set clear expectations and provide constructive feedback, thus enhancing classroom management (Bernardo, 2021). Lastly, teachers were having issues in their adaptability and assertiveness leadership qualities. Some teachers were not that adaptable to diverse learning environments and learner needs, particularly in under-resourced schools where flexibility in teaching methods is essential. The reason is that their adaptability was hindered by rigid curricular standards and limited access to teaching resources (Almario, 2019). Another, some public elementary teachers who were not assertive enough to fairly enforce rules and expectations tending to have problematic classroom management outcomes. Aside from that, many teachers struggle with balancing assertiveness with sensitivity to learners' contexts, often due to a lack of comprehensive training in classroom management techniques (Pantoja, 2020). Locally, public elementary teachers face significant challenges in demonstrating leadership qualities such as

empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness in their classroom behavioral management. One practical issue is the diverse socio-economic backgrounds of learners, which necessitates high levels of empathy; however, many teachers struggle to connect with learners facing various emotional and psychological stresses, thereby hindering their ability to foster a supportive classroom environment (Buan, 2021). Additionally, effective communication is complicated by the multilingual context of Davao City, where teachers must navigate between different dialects and languages, potentially leading to misunderstandings and increased behavioral issues when learners feel unheard or misinterpreted (Timbang, 2020). Furthermore, adaptability is crucial in responding to the varying learning needs and cultural contexts of learners, yet many teachers face constraints due to rigid curricular demands and limited resources, impacting their ability to tailor their teaching methods effectively (Dela Cruz, 2022). Moreover, some teachers struggle to balance assertive classroom management with sensitivity to learners' backgrounds, often resulting in inconsistent enforcement of rules (Ocampo, 2021). Despite the acknowledged importance of leadership qualities in effective classroom management, there is a need for more focused research on how specific leadership strategies impact classroom behavioral management in public elementary schools. Additionally, the variability in classroom dynamics and learner populations across different schools calls for context-specific studies that can offer tailored insights and recommendations (Harris, 2020). Hence, this study seeks to fill this gap by examining the leadership qualities exhibited by public elementary school teachers and their corresponding classroom behavioral management strategies enable to provide insights and recommendations for improving classroom management in public elementary schools.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework— This study is primarily anchored on the Social Learning Theory, developed by Albert Bandura as cited by Higgins et al., (2020) which suggests that people learn from one another through observation, imitation, and modeling. In the classroom, teachers act as role models, and their behavior, attitudes, and responses to situations are observed by their learners. Teachers who demonstrate positive leadership and behavior management strategies can influence their learners to adopt similar behaviors. This theory underlines the importance of teachers exhibiting leadership qualities that promote a positive social environment, where pro-social behavior is modeled and reinforced. Another theory that supports the main theory is the Transformational Leadership Theory which emphasizes the role of leaders in inspiring and motivating followers to achieve their full potential (Bass Avolio, 2019). In the context of public elementary schools, transformational leaders—such as teachers who foster an engaging and supportive classroom environment—can significantly influence learner behavior and academic performance. Research indicates that when teachers adopt transformational leadership qualities, such as empathy, encouragement, and the ability to articulate a clear vision, they create a positive classroom climate that enhances learner engagement and reduces disruptive behaviors (Gonzalez et al., 2020). Such an environment encourages learners to take ownership of their learning and adhere to classroom expectations, thereby improving overall classroom management. The Classroom Management Theory also supports the main theory which emphasizes the importance of creating a structured environment where learners know what is expected of them. Grounded in the work of theorists like Jacob Kounin and Fred Jones as cited by Rogers McNulty (2021), this theory highlights strategies such as clear rules and procedures, effective monitoring, and consistent consequences to enhance learner behavior and engagement. Effective classroom management involves not just discipline but also creating a positive classroom climate that prevents behavior problems by engaging learners in the learning process. Teachers' leadership qualities, such as decisiveness, empathy, and communication skills, are crucial in implementing these strategies effectively. On the other hand, the conceptual framework of the study is shown in Figure 1. The independent variable is the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City in terms of empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness. On the other hand, the dependent variable is the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City in terms of positive reinforcement, clear rules and expectations, use of structured routines, and constructive feedback.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods in conducting the study which are considered strategies or techniques utilized in the collection of data evidence for analysis in order to uncover new information or create better understanding of a topic. Contents of this chapter include the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Paradigm Showing the Variables of the Study

2.1. *Research Design*—This study will employ a descriptive-correlational research design, a method that allows researchers to explore the current state of leadership qualities among teachers and examine how these qualities correlate with their strategies for managing classroom behavior. By utilizing descriptive methods, the researcher can systematically collect data on various aspects of teacher leadership and behavioral management techniques. This approach provides a comprehensive overview of how these variables manifest in the real-world setting of public elementary schools in the Maa District, Division of Davao City. Furthermore, correlational analysis will be employed to identify any significant relationships between the leadership qualities of teachers and their effectiveness in managing classroom behavior. This process has the potential to uncover patterns that could inform teacher training and professional development programs (Fraenkel et al., 2019). Employing a descriptive-correlational design in this context enables the collection of data without manipulating any variables, ensuring that

the natural dynamics between teacher leadership and classroom management strategies are preserved (McMillan Schumacher, 2021). This non-intrusive method offers authentic insights into the practices and challenges faced by public elementary school teachers in the Maa District, Division of Davao City. By maintaining the integrity of the natural educational environment, researchers can gain a true understanding of how teacher leadership qualities and classroom management strategies interact. This approach is essential for providing a realistic depiction of the educational landscape in these schools and serves as a foundation for identifying effective strategies and areas needing improvement (Cohen et al., 2019). Moreover, the descriptive-correlational approach provides a valuable foundation for understanding the complex interplay between teacher leadership and classroom management. By identifying patterns and relationships between these variables, the study can guide further experimental research aimed at testing causality and developing targeted interventions. The insights gained from

this research could significantly inform the design of professional development programs tailored to enhance teacher leadership skills and classroom management strategies. This methodological approach ensures that subsequent studies are built on robust, evidence-based findings, thereby enhancing their validity and applicability to real-world educational settings (Bryman, 2019).

2.2. *Research Ethics*—This study adhered strictly to the established protocols and standard guidelines required for conducting research, particularly in managing respondents' data. The survey questionnaire, along with supporting documentation from authors, was submitted for thorough evaluation. Following approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher will proceed with the study. Social Value. Investigating leadership qualities and classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in the Maa District, Division of Davao City, holds substantial social value as it directly impacts the cultivation of effective educational environments and the holistic development of learners. Teachers' leadership behaviors are closely linked to their professionalism, influencing their ability to create supportive and well-managed classrooms. In addition, this research can identify practices that promote positive learner behavior and academic success by examining the interplay between leadership qualities and behavioral management strategies. Such insights are significant for developing training programs and policies that enhance teacher effectiveness, thereby fostering a culture of respect, responsibility, and ethical behavior among learners. Ultimately, this contributes to the formation of responsible citizens and strengthens the social fabric of the community. Informed Consent. Informed consent is a crucial step in this study, necessitating that participants fully understand the nature of the study, including its purpose, procedures, potential risks, and benefits before agreeing to par-

take. It is important to present this information in an accessible manner, allowing participants to make informed decisions free from coercion. According to McLaughlin et al. (2020), ensuring that participants are adequately informed helps to uphold their autonomy and fosters trust between researchers and participants. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The vulnerability of research participants must also be taken into account, particularly in educational settings where teachers may feel pressured to participate due to hierarchical relationships. Teachers, as professionals, may fear repercussions from school administration or colleagues if they opt out of participation or express dissent. This situation necessitates careful consideration of the power dynamics at play. The researcher will implement strategies to minimize coercion and enhance the comfort of participants. For instance, the study could assure anonymity and confidentiality, which are vital to mitigate concerns about negative repercussions. According to Benatar and Singer (2019), researchers must be especially sensitive to the contexts in which vulnerable populations operate, ensuring their welfare is prioritized throughout the research process. Privacy and Confidentiality. Privacy and confidentiality are essential ethical principles that protect participants' identities and personal information. In the context of studying teachers, it is vital to maintain the confidentiality of their responses, especially when discussing leadership qualities and behavioral management strategies that may reflect their professional capabilities. Data should be anonymized and securely stored, with access limited to the research team. This aligns with the guidelines set forth by the American Psychological Association (2020), which stresses the importance of safeguarding participants' information to foster an environment of trust and openness. The researcher of this study will also ensure that any publication of results does not allow for the identification of individual participants, which can

further enhance their willingness to share honest and candid insights. The Risk, Benefits Safety. The consideration of risks, benefits, and safety is critical in evaluating the ethical dimensions of this research. While the study aims to enhance understanding of effective leadership and classroom management, it is important to assess potential risks, such as emotional distress from discussing challenging experiences or concerns about professional reputation. The researcher of this study will take proactive measures to mitigate these risks, such as providing support resources for participants if they experience discomfort during interviews or surveys. The potential benefits of the research, including improved educational strategies and professional development for teachers, should be clearly communicated to participants to help them understand the significance of their involvement (Fletcher et al., 2021). Justice. The principle of justice mandates that the researcher of this study will treat all participants equitably and ensure that the benefits and burdens of research are distributed fairly. In educational research, this principle implies that the selection of participants should not exploit vulnerable populations, such as teachers who may feel compelled to participate due to institutional pressures. The researcher will ensure that the study benefits all stakeholders, including teachers, learners, and educational institutions, by providing insights that can enhance classroom management practices and leadership qualities (Beauchamp Childress, 2019). Transparency. Transparency in research practices is essential for building trust and credibility. The researcher in this study will openly communicate her intentions, methods, and potential conflicts of interest to participants. This transparency allows teachers to make informed decisions about their participation and helps foster a collaborative environment. Additionally, the results of the research should be shared with the participants and the wider educational community to demonstrate accountability and allow for constructive feedback. As noted by Koocher and Keith-Spiegel (2019), transparency promotes ethical practices and reinforces the commitment to integrity within the research process, enabling participants to understand how their contributions impact educational practices and policies. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher in this study has the necessary skills, knowledge, and experience to conduct the study effectively and ethically. This includes understanding research methodologies, ethical guidelines, and the specific context of elementary home economics education. The researcher also engages in continuous professional development and seek advice from more experienced colleagues or ethics boards when necessary. Ensuring that the researchers are well-qualified helps to protect participants and enhances the validity and reliability of the study findings (Resnik, 2018). Additionally, the researcher is enrolled in the thesis development course which means all the pre-requisite courses and requirements were already completed. Adequacy of Facilities. The adequacy of facilities is a critical ethical consideration that ensures the safety and comfort of participants during the research process. In studies involving teachers, it is vital that the research environment is conducive to open discussion and reflection on leadership qualities and classroom management strategies. Researchers should provide appropriate facilities, such as quiet meeting spaces or virtual platforms, to facilitate honest dialogue. Moreover, ensuring that participants have access to necessary resources, such as educational materials or professional support, can significantly enhance their experience and the quality of the data collected. The American Educational Research Association (2020) emphasizes the importance of creating supportive environments that allow participants to express their insights without discomfort or distraction. Community Involvement. Community involvement is another crucial ethical aspect that enhances

the relevance and applicability of research findings. Engaging with the community, including teachers, school administrators, and parents, can provide valuable insights into the specific challenges and needs within educational settings. This participatory approach fosters a sense of ownership among community members and ensures that the research addresses real-world issues. Furthermore, it can help build a supportive network for implementing changes based on the research findings, ultimately benefiting the educational environment. According to Minkler and Wallerstein (2019), community involvement not only enriches the research process but also promotes ethical practices by prioritizing the voices and experiences of those most affected by the study.

2.3. Research Respondents—This investigation was carried out within the designated elementary schools situated in Maa District, Division of Davao City. A total of one hundred and twenty (120) public elementary school teachers participated as respondents in this research endeavor. The respondents were male and female, aged between 30 to 50 years, with an average teaching experience of 10 to 20 years. Most held bachelor's degrees in elementary education. Relatively, the sample size 120 was determined to be sufficient for achieving statistical power and ensuring the reliability of the study's findings. The chosen sample size enabled the inclusion of teachers from various public high schools, thus capturing a wide array of perspectives and practices. The selection of respondents was facilitated through purposive sampling, which represents a prevalent method of selection not contingent upon probability. Purposive sampling, being a non-probability sampling technique, is chosen for its practicality and expediency in gathering data from readily available participants within the specified context. In employing purposive sampling, the researchers purposefully selected elemen-

tary teachers from targeted schools within Maa District of Davao City based on their relevance to the study's objectives. This method allows for a focused exploration of the perceptions and practices of teachers regarding teacher feedback and learner progress in elementary education (Johnson, 2021). Moreover, purposive sampling aligns with the research objectives by ensuring that participants selected have direct experience and insights relevant to the study's focus, thereby enhancing the depth and relevance of the findings (Smith Jones, 2020).

2.4. Research Instrument—Crafting research instruments is a crucial phase in the research process as they facilitate data collection and information gathering from participants. These instruments are essential for ensuring the quality and validity of research outcomes. Properly designed research instruments enable accurate measurement of variables, yielding reliable data (Huck, 2019). Additionally, they standardize data collection, allowing for the replication of studies and comparison of results across various contexts (Cohen et al., 2019). In this study, the researcher employed a survey questionnaire as the primary tool for data collection. The survey was consisted of two parts, addressing the two variables under investigation. For the first part of the survey instrument, this would provide data on the level of leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City in terms of empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness. Questions from this part of the instrument were adopted from the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ) by Avolio and Bass (2004). In the process of interpreting its data, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Range Descriptive Equivalent and Interpretation of Leadership Qualities of Public Elementary School Teachers

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	The leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers are always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	The leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers are often evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	The leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers are sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	The leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers are seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	The leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers are not evident.

For the second part of the questionnaire, this determined the level of classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City in terms of positive reinforcement, clear rules and expectations, use of structured routines, and constructive feedback. Questions from this part of the instrument were adopted from the Classroom Management Strategies

Scale (CMSS) by Emmer and Stough (2021). The same with the first part of the survey questionnaire, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest in interpreting its data. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Moreover, thorough development of research instruments enhances construct validity by ensuring that the items or questions included correspond with the intended constructs or concepts under investigation (Huck, 2019). Additionally, clear and concise research instruments improve participants' comprehension and cooperation, which is crucial for obtaining high-quality data. Ultimately, the development of

research instruments bolsters the credibility and rigor of research findings, making it a vital part of the research process. Specifically, the instrument's validity was confirmed by research experts and panel committee members. The survey instrument also undergone pilot testing to determine its reliability, which was computed using Cronbach's Alpha.

Range Descriptive Level and Interpretation of Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	The classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers are always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	The classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers are often evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderate	The classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers are sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	The classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers are seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Very Low	The classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers are not evident.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—In the initial phase of the data collection process, the researcher drafted a formal letter seeking authorization from the Dean of the Graduate School to proceed with the proposed research endeavor. Subsequently, another letter was prepared, soliciting permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao Del Sur, routed through the designated channels of the Office of Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS) affiliated with the selected schools. Following the receipt of the requisite permits, the survey questionnaire was finalized for implementation in the study. Upon commence-

ment of the study, the researcher personally distributes the survey questionnaire to the designated respondents with the permission and guidance of the school principal where the target respondents are teaching. Subsequent to the respondents’ completion of the survey questions, the researcher promptly retrieved the questionnaires. Lastly, the amassed data undergone analysis conducted by a professional statistician utilizing various methodologies delineated within the preceding chapters. The findings resulting from the data analysis was interpreted to provide additional insights pertinent to the study’s objectives.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The study used the respondents’ collected data for analysis. The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this

study to uncover meaningful insights from collected data. Mean. Utilizing statistical measures specifically the mean offers a foundational understanding of central tendencies within the

data, providing a preliminary overview of prevalent practices and attitudes among elementary teachers (Rumsey, 2020). Calculating the mean scores of various leadership qualities and classroom management strategies can reveal initial patterns among teachers in the Maa District, Division of Davao City. This step is essential for identifying trends and establishing a baseline for more complex analyses, as the mean provides a snapshot of the average scenario within the educational environment. Consequently, the researcher used this baseline to explore variances and correlations, thereby enhancing the overall analysis (Heavey, 2019). Pearson R Correlation. The Pearson's R, or Pearson correlation coefficient, extends the analysis by quantifying the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two variables (Warne, 2020). In this study, Pearson's R was used to investigate the connection between specific leadership qualities, such as empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness, and effective classroom behavioral management strategies. This statistical tool helps determine whether a positive or negative correlation exists, offering insights into how enhancing certain leadership qualities could impact classroom management outcomes. A significant correlation coefficient would indicate that fostering partic-

ular leadership qualities among teachers might lead to improved classroom behavior management, thereby guiding targeted professional development programs (Rumsey, 2020). Multiple Linear Regression. Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis advances the exploration of variable relationships by examining the impact of multiple independent variables, such as leadership qualities (empathy, effective communication, adaptability, assertiveness) and effective classroom behavioral management strategies, on a single dependent variable, classroom management effectiveness. This analysis is particularly valuable in educational research as it considers the complex interplay of various factors that contribute to teaching effectiveness (Kith, 2019). By applying MLR, the researcher can determine the relative contribution of different leadership qualities to successful classroom management while controlling for other variables in the model (Warne, 2020). This can reveal, for instance, whether certain qualities have a more significant impact on management strategies or if the interaction between different qualities yields the best outcomes. Such insights can inform the design of comprehensive teacher training programs that address multiple facets of leadership development.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions based on the data gathered after the conduct of this study. This includes the interpretation of the data and the repercussions of the findings of the study. The deliberations presented in this chapter are aligned to the statement of the problem cited in the previous chapters of this study.

3.1. Level of Leadership Qualities of Public Elementary School Teachers—Summary of the Level of Leadership Qualities of Public Elementary School Teachers. Shown in Table 1 is the analysis of the level of the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The table also

presented the analysis of each indicator of of the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers such as empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness. Based on the analysis presented in the table, the high mean score of 3.76 across these leadership qualities suggests that the leadership qualities of pub-

lic elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are often evident. This implies that the public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City, are proficient in key areas that contribute to effective educational leadership. These high scores further imply that teachers are capable of creating supportive, communicative, adaptable, and well-managed classroom environments. Such

leadership qualities are essential for fostering learner success and well-being, as well as for promoting a culture of continuous improvement and professional development among teachers (Leithwood et al., 2020). By maintaining high standards in these leadership dimensions, teachers can ensure that their learners receive a high-quality education that prepares them for future challenges and opportunities.

Table 1. Summary of the Level of Leadership Qualities of Public Elementary School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Empathy	3.86	High
Effective Communication	3.72	High
Adaptability	3.63	High
Assertiveness	3.85	High
Overall	3.76	High

Specifically, the said table displaying the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City, indicates a high level of proficiency across various critical dimensions. First, the empathy score of 3.86 which ranked top among the other indicators of leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers. This level of analysis implies that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are frequently able to understand and respond to their learners’ emotional needs and perspectives. Empathy in educational leadership is vital as it fosters a supportive and inclusive learning environment where learners feel understood and valued (Cooper, 2021). Public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City were empathetic teachers which can build stronger relationships with their learners, which enhances learner engagement and motivation, ultimately leading to improved academic outcomes and overall well-being. Second, the effective communication, with a mean

score of 3.72, highlights the public elementary school teachers’ ability to clearly articulate expectations, provide feedback, and foster open dialogue with learners, parents, and colleagues. Effective communication is crucial in education as it ensures that all stakeholders are aligned and informed, facilitating the smooth implementation of educational initiatives and policies (Epstein, 2019). This further implies that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City used clear and open communication that helps build trust and rapport between them and the learners, which is fundamental for creating a positive and supportive classroom climate. This strong foundation in communication skills ensures that learners feel heard and valued, which is essential for their academic and personal development. Third, the adaptability mean score of 3.63 is considered at the bottom analysis but still with high descriptive rating. This implies that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are capable of adjusting

their teaching methods and strategies to meet diverse learner needs and respond to changing classroom dynamics. Adaptability is essential in education as it enables teachers to effectively handle various challenges, such as integrating new technologies, addressing diverse learning styles, and modifying lesson plans in response to learner feedback and performance (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019). By being adaptable, public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City can create more inclusive and responsive learning environments, thereby improving learner engagement and academic outcomes. Additionally, adaptability in educational leadership supports continuous improvement and innovation in teaching practices, which is essential for fostering a culture of lifelong learning and resilience among learners. Lastly, the assertiveness mean score of 3.85 reflects the teachers' ability to confidently enforce classroom rules, advocate for learners' needs, and address issues constructively. Assertiveness in educational leadership ensures that teachers can effectively communicate their expectations, establish clear boundaries, and maintain classroom discipline (Hattie, 2019). By being assertive teachers, public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City can address issues directly and confidently, contributing to a well-managed classroom environment where learners understand the rules and feel secure. This ability to assertively lead and communicate is essential for promoting a positive and productive learning atmosphere, ultimately enhancing learner outcomes and teacher effectiveness.

Relatively, the individual indicator contributes uniquely to this overall rating. Specifically, the first indicator, Positive Reinforcement, with a mean score of 3.57, implies the frequent use of praise and rewards by the public elementary school teachers in Maa District,

3.2. *Level of Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers*—Summary of the Level of Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers. Shown in Table 2 is the insightful overview of the level of classroom behavioral management strategies employed by public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The table also presented the analysis of each indicator of the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers such as positive reinforcement, clear rules and expectations, the use of structured routines, and constructive feedback. Based on the analysis presented in the table, the high mean score of 3.65 across these classroom behavioral management strategies suggests that the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are often evident. This implies that it is evident that the said teachers are effectively implementing various strategies to manage classroom behavior. This further implies that the use of positive reinforcement, clear rules and expectations, structured routines, and constructive feedback by the public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City collectively contribute to a positive and structured learning environment. These practices not only help in minimizing behavioral issues but also promote learner engagement and academic success. The high overall mean score depicts the proficiency and dedication of the said teachers in creating a conducive learning environment through effective classroom management strategies.

Division of Davao City to encourage positive behavior among learners. Positive reinforcement is a critical strategy in classroom management as it helps to reinforce desirable behaviors and increase their likelihood of recurrence (Simonsen et al., 2021). This approach not only

Table 2. Summary of the Level of Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Positive Reinforcement	3.57	High
Clear Rules and Expectations	3.64	High
Use of Structured Routines	3.85	High
Constructive Feedback	3.57	High
Overall	3.65	High

promotes a positive classroom environment but also enhances learner motivation and engagement (Conroy et al., 2020). By consistently acknowledging and rewarding good behavior, public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City can create a supportive atmosphere where learners feel valued and motivated to meet behavioral expectations. Next the second indicator which is the Clear Rules and Expectations, scoring 3.64, implies that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City ensure that classroom rules are well-defined and communicated to learners. Clearly outlining rules and expectations at the beginning of the school year and consistently reinforcing them helps to establish a predictable and stable learning environment (Simonsen et al., 2021). This practice reduces ambiguity and provides learners with a clear understanding of acceptable behaviors, thereby minimizing disruptions and promoting a sense of order (Marzano, 2021). Public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City believed that involving learners in the creation or review of classroom rules can further enhance their commitment to following these guidelines, as they feel a sense of ownership and responsibility. The highest scoring indicator, Use of Structured Routines, with a mean of 3.85, implies the importance of establishing and maintaining daily routines. Structured routines help learners understand what is expected of them at various times throughout the day, which can significantly reduce behavioral issues and transition times (Doyle, 2020). The high score in this category indicates that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are proficient in creating and maintaining routines that learners are familiar with and follow consistently. Regular review of these routines, especially after breaks, ensures that learners remain aware of the expected behaviors, further reinforcing the structured environment. Lastly, the Constructive Feedback indicator, also with a mean score of 3.57, points to the regular use of feedback as a tool for behavioral improvement. Constructive feedback focuses on specific behaviors rather than the individual, providing learners with clear guidance on how to improve (Brookhart, 2020). Public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City believed that this approach is crucial for fostering a growth mindset among learners, encouraging them to view mistakes as opportunities for learning rather than. The balance of corrective and positive feedback ensures that learners remain motivated and do not feel discouraged, promoting a positive and supportive classroom environment. The overall high score of 3.65 for classroom behavioral management strategies reflects a strong commitment by teachers in Maa District to maintaining effective classroom management practices. These strategies are essential for creating an environment conducive to learning, where learners feel safe, respected, and motivated to succeed (Evertson

Weinstein, 2013). The consistent implementation of these strategies indicates that teachers are well-equipped with the skills and knowledge necessary to manage diverse classroom behaviors effectively (Lewis, Romi, Qui, Katz, 2005).

3.3. *Significant Relationship between the Leadership Qualities and Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers*—Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis using Pearson correlation coefficient (r) on the significant relationship be-

tween the leadership qualities and classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate how these leadership qualities influence the effectiveness of behavioral management strategies employed by the said teachers. The correlation coefficients (r-values) indicate the strength and direction of the relationships, while the p-values reveal the statistical significance of these relationships.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between Leadership Qualities and Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers

Leadership Qualities	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Empathy	0.516	0.000	Reject
Effective Communication	0.418	0.000	Reject
Adaptability	0.583	0.000	Reject
Assertiveness	0.200	0.029	Reject
Overall	0.866	0.000	Reject

Based on the presented analysis, the overall correlation coefficient of 0.866 with a p-value equal to 0.000 indicates a strong positive relationship between leadership qualities and classroom behavioral management strategies, implying that effective leadership of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City is integral to successful of their classroom management. This comprehensive relationship emphasizes the interconnectedness of various public elementary school teachers' leadership qualities and their collective influence on their approaches to managing classroom behavior. Educational stakeholders should consider integrating leadership training as a fundamental aspect of teacher education programs to enhance the overall quality of teaching (Odom et al., 2020; Reddy et al., 2021). This finding further implies in the extension of policy development, as schools may need to adopt systemic

changes that prioritize leadership development as a strategy to improve behavioral outcomes in classrooms across the district. Given that all reported p-values are less than 0.05, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected across all leadership qualities assessed, indicating a significant positive correlation between leadership qualities and classroom management strategies. First, the indicator Empathy, with a correlation coefficient of 0.516, demonstrates a moderate positive relationship with classroom behavioral management strategies. This finding implies that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City who exhibit high levels of empathy are more likely to employ effective management strategies in their classrooms. Empathetic teachers are better equipped to understand their learners' emotional needs, enabling them to create supportive learning environments that enhance learner engagement

and behavior (Hamzah et al., 2020). Furthermore, the importance of empathy in education aligns with research indicating that emotionally intelligent teachers can more effectively handle classroom disruptions and foster positive learner-teacher relationships (Kraft Papay, 2020). The implications of this finding underscore the need for teacher training programs of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City to emphasize the development of empathetic qualities as a core component of effective leadership in education. Second, the Effective Communication indicator shows a significant moderate positive relationship with classroom behavioral management strategies, as indicated by a correlation coefficient of 0.418 with a p-value equal to 0.000. Effective communication is vital for teachers to convey expectations, provide feedback, and engage learners in the learning process (Peled Baruch, 2020). The ability to communicate effectively can enhance classroom dynamics by promoting clarity and understanding, thereby reducing misbehavior and fostering a cooperative learning environment (Mason et al., 2020). This finding implies that professional development programs for public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City should focus on enhancing communication skills as a means to improve classroom management practices. Schools may also benefit from adopting a comprehensive approach to communication, including strategies for active listening and constructive feedback. Third, the leadership quality of adaptability, with the highest correlation coefficient of 0.583 with a p-value equal to 0.000, still indicates a moderate positive relationship with classroom behavioral management strategies. Adaptability in teaching practices allows teachers to respond effectively to the diverse needs of their learners and the dynamic nature of classroom environments (Dumay et al., 2020; Davis Pappano, 2021). This implies that public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Di-

vision of Davao City can adjust their strategies based on situational demands are more likely to maintain control and order in the classroom, which is critical for effective teaching and learning. Further implications of this finding suggest that fostering adaptability among teachers should be a priority for educational leadership and administration. Training programs that emphasize flexible teaching approaches can significantly enhance the said teachers' capabilities in managing classroom behavior and addressing individual learner needs. Finally, the Assertiveness, with a correlation coefficient of 0.200 with a p-value equal to 0.029, reveals a weaker yet still significant relationship with classroom behavioral management strategies. This finding implies that assertive teachers such as the public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are more likely to implement effective strategies for managing classroom behavior, albeit to a lesser extent than the other leadership qualities examined. Assertiveness enables teachers to establish clear boundaries and expectations while maintaining respectful interactions with learners (Hutton et al., 2020). This quality is crucial for creating a classroom environment where learners feel secure and understand the consequences of their behavior (McKenzie et al., 2020). Consequently, the implications of this finding highlight the importance of developing assertiveness training within professional development programs for the said teachers to bolster their classroom management effectiveness.

3.4. Regression Analysis of the Leadership Qualities on Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies of Public Elementary School Teachers —The regression analysis shown in the Table 4 reveals critical insights into how leadership qualities impact the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in the Maa District of Davao City. The unstandardized coefficients (B) indicate the direct effect of each leader-

ship quality on classroom management, while the standardized coefficients (Beta) allow for comparisons across different variables. With an R-value of 0.919 and an R² of 0.845, the regression analysis demonstrates a strong relationship between the leadership qualities and classroom management strategies, suggesting that approximately 84.5percent of the variance in classroom behavioral management can be explained by these leadership qualities. The overall significance of the regression is confirmed by the F-value of 332.080 with a p-value of 0.000, indicating that at least one predictor variable significantly contributes to the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in the Maa District of Davao City. Hence, the hypothesis that none of the indicators of leadership qualities significantly influence the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City is rejected. Specifically, the Empathy indica-

tor emerges as a significant predictor of classroom behavioral management strategies with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.247 and a standardized coefficient of 0.382, both statistically significant (p < 0.001). This suggests that for each unit increase in empathy, there is a corresponding increase in the effectiveness of classroom management strategies. This finding is consistent with research highlighting the role of teacher empathy in fostering a positive classroom environment, as empathetic teachers can better understand and respond to learner needs, thereby improving engagement and reducing behavioral issues (Noddings, 2020; Rororda et al., 2021). The implications of this finding underscore the necessity for teacher training programs public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City to incorporate empathy development, enhancing teachers' abilities to connect with learners and manage classroom dynamics effectively.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of the School Leadership on the Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

Leadership Qualities	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho
(Constant)	0.206	0.126		1.634	0.005	
Empathy	0.247	0.021	0.382	11.585	0.000	Reject
Effective Communication	0.341	0.038	0.545	8.900	0.000	Failed to Reject
Adaptability	0.392	0.014	0.819	28.528	0.000	Reject
Assertiveness	0.056	0.037	0.091	1.518	0.132	Failed to Reject
R		0.919	R²		0.845	
F-Value		332.080	p-value		0.000	

Another, the Effective Communication indicator significantly contributes to classroom behavioral management strategies, with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.341 and a standardized coefficient of 0.545. The p-value equal to 0.000 indicates a strong level of significance, suggesting that effective communication plays a crucial role in the management of classroom behaviors.

Teachers who communicate effectively can articulate expectations, provide feedback, and foster an environment of collaboration and understanding (Roth Ginsburg, 2020; Scherer et al., 2021). The strong relationship between effective communication and classroom management implies that public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City should priori-

tize the development of communication skills in teacher training programs, as it is foundational to establishing a classroom culture where learners feel valued and understood, ultimately leading to improved behavioral outcomes. Consequently, the Adaptability indicator, with an unstandardized coefficient of 0.392 and a standardized coefficient of 0.819, demonstrates the most substantial effect on classroom management strategies among the leadership qualities analyzed. The statistical significance of this variable highlights the importance of a teacher's ability to adapt to changing classroom situations and diverse learner needs (Dumay et al., 2020; Schunk, 2021). Adaptable teachers especially in the public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City can modify their instructional approaches and management strategies in response to various challenges, which is essential for maintaining order and promoting positive behaviors among learners. The implications of this finding suggest that training programs should emphasize adaptability as a key leadership quality, equipping teachers with the skills necessary to navigate the complexities of classroom dynamics effectively. In contrast, assertiveness presents an unstandardized coefficient of 0.056 and a standardized coefficient of 0.091, indicating a weaker influence on classroom management strategies compared to other leadership qualities. The p-value of 0.132 suggests that assertiveness does not significantly predict effective classroom management within this sample. While assertiveness can contribute to establishing boundaries and expectations, its lesser impact may indicate that other qualities, such as empathy and adaptability, play more substantial roles in influencing learner behavior (Hutton et al., 2020; Reddy et al., 2021). This finding implies the need for a balanced approach in teacher training, emphasizing that while assertiveness is valuable, it should be complemented by empathy and adaptability for optimal classroom management. Furthermore, the overall regression analysis strength, as indicated by the R^2 value of 0.845, signifies the collective importance of the said leadership qualities in influencing classroom behavioral management strategies in public elementary school in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The analysis also suggests that by enhancing leadership qualities such as empathy, effective communication, and adaptability, the public elementary schools in Maa District, Division of Davao City can significantly improve teachers' abilities to manage classroom behaviors effectively. These findings have profound implications for educational policy and practice, advocating for the integration of leadership development into teacher education programs (Odom et al., 2020; Scherer et al., 2021). By prioritizing these qualities, educational institutions can create environments that support both teacher effectiveness and learner success, fostering a culture of learning that accommodates diverse learner needs and promotes positive behaviors.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings of the study based on the outcome of the gathered data. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—Teachers with robust leadership abilities can effectively establish clear expectations, consistently enforce rules, and address disruptive behavior with confidence and fairness. Despite this, many public elementary school teachers encounter challenges in

managing classroom behaviors. Some teachers struggle to forge connections with their learners, which exacerbates behavioral problems, while others find communication difficulties lead to misunderstandings and unclear classroom expectations. Additionally, new teachers often face challenges in addressing the diverse needs of learners, which can result in disengagement and misbehavior, as well as difficulties in enforcing rules and maintaining classroom discipline. In this study, a non-experimental quantitative research methodology using a descriptive correlation approach was applied. Statistical analyses such as the mean, Pearson R correlation, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized. The participants in the research were the one hundred and twenty (120) public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. The respondents will be male and female, aged between 30 to 50 years, with an average teaching experience of 10 to 20 years. Most held bachelor's degrees in elementary education. These respondents were chosen via a sample process known as purposive sampling. Data were analyzed based on the survey questionnaires that were used by the researcher after they had been modified to conform to the parameters of the study, which had been subjected to validation by experts and had its reliability examined. Descriptive results of the study revealed that the level of leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers received a high descriptive level rating which means that the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City is often evident. Likewise, the level of classroom behavioral management strategies of the said public elementary school teachers received a high descriptive level rating which means that the behavioral management strategies of these public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City are often evident. Consequently, there is a strong positive relationship between leadership qualities

and classroom behavioral management strategies, implying that effective leadership of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City is integral to successful of their classroom management. Likewise, the regression analysis resulted that all of the indicators of leadership qualities such as empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness significantly influence the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: There is a high level of proficiency in the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City specifically in key areas such as empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness. This suggests that teachers in this district are well-equipped to create supportive, communicative, adaptable, and well-managed classroom environments, which are crucial for fostering learner success and well-being. This high proficiency in these leadership dimensions supports a culture of continuous improvement and professional development among teachers, ensuring learners receive a high-quality education that prepares them for future challenges and opportunities. Relatively, there is also a high level of proficiency in employing effective techniques such as positive reinforcement, clear rules and expectations, structured routines, and constructive feedback in the classroom behavioral management strategies among public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This indicates that teachers are adept at creating a positive and structured learning environment, which is essential for minimizing behavioral issues and promoting learner engagement and academic success. The dedication and skillfulness of these teachers in implementing these strategies underscore their commitment to fostering an educational

setting where learners feel valued, motivated, and equipped to meet behavioral and academic expectations. Furthermore, there is a strong positive relationship between the leadership qualities of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City, and their classroom behavioral management strategies. This significant correlation indicates that teachers who exhibit strong leadership qualities such as empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness are more likely to implement effective classroom management strategies. Educational stakeholders should prioritize integrating leadership training into teacher education programs and consider policy developments that emphasize leadership development, as these strategies are integral to creating a supportive and structured learning environment that enhances learner engagement and behavior. Moreover, there is a significant impact of leadership qualities on the classroom behavioral management strategies of public elementary school teachers in the Maa District of Davao City, explaining a substantial portion of the variance in these strategies. Notably, qualities such as empathy, effective communication, and adaptability emerged as critical predictors, suggesting that enhancing these attributes can profoundly improve classroom management and learner behavior. These highlight the necessity for educational stakeholders to integrate leadership development into teacher training programs, ensuring that teachers are equipped with the essential skills to foster a positive, structured, and effective learning environment.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: To enhance the already high level of proficiency among teachers in the Maa District, the Department of Education Officials should integrate focused leadership training programs that emphasize empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness into ongoing professional development initiatives

such as Empathy Development Workshops, Effective Communication Skills Training, Adaptability and Flexibility in Classroom Management, Assertiveness and Boundaries Setting for Teachers, Classroom Behavioral Management Strategies Training. Additionally, policies should be developed to support and sustain these training programs such as Policy for Mandatory Leadership Development for New Teachers, Continuous Professional Development (CPD) for Leadership Qualities, Peer Mentoring Program for Classroom Management, Integration of Leadership Qualities in Teacher Evaluation, and Incentives for Leadership Excellence in Education to ensure that teachers will continuously improve their classroom management strategies. By prioritizing these leadership qualities, the department can further foster a supportive, communicative, and adaptable educational environment that maximizes learner engagement and academic success. School administrators in Maa District, Division of Davao City should prioritize fostering the continued development of teachers' leadership qualities, particularly in empathy, communication, adaptability, and assertiveness, as these have shown to significantly enhance classroom management. Additionally, administrators should support and facilitate ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers, focusing on effective classroom management techniques such as positive reinforcement, structured routines, and feedback. Lastly, administrators should advocate for the integration of leadership and management training within the teacher evaluation system to further promote the use of these essential skills in creating positive and productive learning environments. Public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City should continue to build on their strengths in leadership qualities such as empathy, effective communication, adaptability, and assertiveness, as these have proven essential for fostering positive classroom environments. Teach-

ers are encouraged to further refine their classroom management strategies by consistently applying techniques like positive reinforcement, clear rules, and structured routines to enhance learner engagement and minimize behavioral challenges. Additionally, teachers should actively participate in professional development opportunities that focus on enhancing their leadership skills to ensure continued success in creating a supportive and effective learning environment. Learners in Maa District, Division of Davao City are encouraged to take full advantage of the supportive and well-managed classroom environments created by their teachers, who demonstrate strong leadership qualities such as empathy, communication, and adaptability. It is important for learners to engage actively in the structured learning environment, following classroom rules and expectations, and participating in feedback opportunities to foster their academic success. Additionally, learners should continue to support and collaborate with their teachers in maintaining a positive classroom atmosphere that encourages mutual respect and learning. Future researchers are encouraged to further investigate the specific impact of individual leadership qualities such as empathy, communication, adaptability, and assertiveness on learner outcomes, particularly focusing on long-term academic and behavioral developments. It would also be valuable to explore how various classroom management strategies interact with these leadership qualities across different educational contexts and grade levels to gain a deeper understanding of their effectiveness. Additionally, future studies could examine the role of leadership training in enhancing these skills among teachers and its direct impact on learner engagement and success in diverse classroom settings.

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